
SIGMA-EST and DATA SUBMISSION

OPERATIVE MANUAL

SIGMA EST Version 2.0.0

Manual Version 3.0

The present technical report aims to provide guidance to the users of the SIGMA EST mapping tool. [SIGMA-EST](#) is a web tool that supports data providers with data preparation. It allows reporting countries to map the data stored in their national databases to the EFSA data models and to generate XML files ready to be uploaded to the Data Collection Framework (DCF).

Contents

DATA MAPPING	3
1. INTRODUCTION: THE VIEWER	3
2. ATTRIBUTE MAPPING	5
2.1. General instructions.....	5
2.2. Attribute mapping cases	11
2.3. Edit.....	13
3. CATALOGUE MAPPING.....	14
3.1. General instructions.....	14
3.2. Catalogue mapping cases	16
4. FILE TRANSLATION	19
5. DOWNLOAD OF THE TRANSLATED XML FILE	21
6. AMENDMENT	22

DATA MAPPING

The **data mapping** is the process through which the users define the relationship between the variables (attributes) and values of their national data model and the respective ones of the EFSA data models. In the SIGMA-EST vocabulary, each data model within a specific data collection is called “**Activity**”. As an example, the ASF data collection has two Activities: the pig population data and the ASF laboratory data.

An Activity is typically composed by one or more Entities. An Entity is a conceptual grouping of a set of **attributes**. Each attribute has individual properties, i.e., the values that are reported for a given attribute. These values can:

- be reported as a primary value (text or number)
- refer and be linked to a predefined list of values (catalogue) created by EFSA.

The data mapping must be performed both at attribute and at catalogue level (when applicable). More in detail:

- each mandatory EFSA attribute must be associated to one or more national variables
- if a mandatory EFSA attribute is associated to a catalogue, each national value must be associated to an EFSA catalogue value

Outcome: the result of the data mapping process generates a schema that reflects the matching between the national database and the EFSA data model, taking into account the attributes and terminology used by both sides (reporting country/EFSA).

The steps to be performed for a complete data mapping are the following and in this exact order:

- Attribute mapping
- Catalogue mapping.

1. INTRODUCTION: THE VIEWER

The **Viewer** section allows the users to explore the EFSA data model and the relationship among its components, their current mapping (if existent) and to search the list of available catalogues. The users can:

1. Click on the **Viewer** tab (Figure 1, action1)
 - 1.1. Click on **Activities** from the dropdown menu (action 2)
 - 1.2. Select the activity of interest (e.g., Pig-Population) (action 3)

Figure 1

- 1.3. Click on the + / - signs to open/close the sublevels of the data model respectively and to visualise the structure (Figure 2, action 4)
- 1.4. Click on the button 'Print Schema Attributes' to download the list and description of all the attributes related to the activity of interest (Figure 2)
- 1.5. Click on the button 'Show mapping' to have a check on the existing mapping (Figure 2)

Figure 2

2. Click on the **Viewer** tab (Figure 3, action1)
 - 2.1. Click on the **Catalogue** (action 2).
 - 2.2. Select the catalogue of interest from the drop-down menu and see all the included catalogue values (action 3).
 - 2.3. Click on the 'Download Catalogue' button to download the catalogue in Excel format.

Figure 3

2. ATTRIBUTE MAPPING

2.1. General instructions

In this section, general instructions are provided to the users in order to complete their attribute mapping successfully. The users can map the attributes from their national database to the respective EFSA data model, thus creating a relationship between national attributes and EFSA attributes.

- If the users have already completed their mapping and they wish to proceed with their file translation, they can follow the relevant steps in the Section 4 '[FILE TRANSLATION](#)'.
- If the users have already completed their mapping and they wish to edit it, they can follow the relevant steps in the Section 2.3 '[Edit](#)'.
- If the users are new and want to perform their attribute mapping, they can follow the steps below:
 1. Click on the **Map** tab (Figure 4, action 1) and then on **Entity** (action 2)
 2. Select from the drop-down menu the Activity of interest (e.g., Pig-Population) (action 3)
 3. Click on the 'Upload file' button and select the Excel file containing the national data to be uploaded. The file should contain in the first row the names/variables extracted from the national database and, optionally, the data to translate.

Figure 4

4. Click on the button with the upload icon and the name of the excel file (Figure 5).

Figure 5

5. A preview table will appear with the national names in the left column and the EFSA entities and attributes in the right column (Figure 6). The users can

have an overview of the attributes in both parts. Click on the 'Next' button to proceed.

Figure 6

6. The users must map the national names to the EFSA attributes. The link can be created by dragging' and 'dropping the relevant national name to the respective EFSA attribute. **Please note that the attribute mapping is considered completed when all the EFSA attributes have the tick sign in front of them** (Figure 7). In case the users don't have a national name to correspond to an optional EFSA attribute, they should right-click on it and choose the 'Not Available' option. (Figure 14).
7. Click on the 'Next' button once the attribute mapping has been completed (Figure 7).

Figure 7

8. A summary table with the implemented attribute mapping will be displayed. In case a mistake is spotted, click on the 'Previous' button to return to the previous stage of the mapping and revert the erroneous mapping. To remove the wrong association, the users simply right-click on the EFSA attribute that you want to disassociate and select 'Revert'. If the mapping is correct, click on the 'Next' button for confirmation (Figure 8).

Entity Name	Your attribute name	Main Attribute name	Catalogue Type	Mapping Type
ESTABLISHMENT	estabCode	estabId	VARCHAR	VARCHAR
ESTABLISHMENT	type	estabType	CATALOGUE[ESTABLISHMENT TYPE]	SIMPLE
ESTABLISHMENT	employees	estabPers	NUMBER	NUMBER
ESTABLISHMENT	precision	estabCoordPrecision	CATALOGUE[COORDINATES PRECISION]	SIMPLE
ESTABLISHMENT	x	estabXCoord	NUMBER	NUMBER
ESTABLISHMENT	y	estabYCoord	NUMBER	NUMBER
ESTABLISHMENT	municipality	estabMunicipality	CATALOGUE[LOCAL ADMINISTRATIVE UNITS]	SIMPLE
ESTABLISHMENT	area	estabArea	CATALOGUE[NUTS]	SIMPLE
SUB_UNIT	subCode	subUnitId	VARCHAR	VARCHAR
SUB_UNIT	species	subUnitSpecies	CATALOGUE[SPECIES]	SIMPLE
SUB_UNIT	purpose	subUnitPurpType	CATALOGUE[SUBUNIT PURPOSE TYPE]	SIMPLE
SUB_UNIT	Not Available	subUnitReplevel	CATALOGUE[REPRODUCTIVE LEVEL]	NOTUSED
SUB_UNIT	Not Available	subUnitCapacity	NUMBER	NOTUSED
SUB_UNIT	animals	subUnitActualNumber	NUMBER	NUMBER
SUB_UNIT	prod	subUnitProdType	CATALOGUE[SUBUNIT LOCATION]	SIMPLE
SUB_UNIT	inherit(precision)	subUnitCoordPrecision	INHERIT	INHERIT
SUB_UNIT	inherit(x)	subUnitXCoord	INHERIT	INHERIT
SUB_UNIT	inherit(y)	subUnitYCoord	INHERIT	INHERIT
SUB_UNIT	inherit(municipality)	subUnitMunicipality	INHERIT	INHERIT
SUB_UNIT	inherit(area)	subUnitArea	INHERIT	INHERIT
SUB_UNIT	day	recordCensusD	NUMBER	NUMBER
SUB_UNIT	month	recordCensusM	NUMBER	NUMBER
SUB_UNIT	year	recordCensusY	NUMBER	NUMBER
SUB_UNIT	record	recordId	VARCHAR	VARCHAR
SUB_UNIT	Not Available	amType	VARCHAR	NOTUSED

Figure 8

9. Click on the 'Yes' button to activate the upload of the values contained in the national file. The values will be available for catalogue mapping automatically (Figure 9, action 1).
10. Click on the 'Finish' button to generate the schema and complete the attribute mapping (action 2). A pop-up success message will appear, and a confirmation email will be sent to the user stating the completion of the mapping.

Figure 9

Important tips and key points of attention

Every national attribute name that is dragged and dropped on the correspondent EFSA attribute on the right side, is considered mapped. In detail:

- All mandatory EFSA attributes must be mapped to a name from the national file. In case that a mandatory attribute has not been mapped, an error message will appear warning the user.
- All the mandatory EFSA attributes are indicated with red letters, the optional ones with black and conditional attributes in green (Figure 10, point 1).
- All attribute types are described in square brackets next to the EFSA attribute name (e.g., CATALOGUE NAME, NUMBER, VARCHAR) (Figure 10, point 2).
- If a name from the national file has been mapped to an EFSA attribute of primitive type (text or numerical value), then the name is no longer draggable, and a fully colored square will appear next to it (Figure 10, point 3).
- If a name from the national file has been mapped to an EFSA attribute of catalogue type, then the name is still available to be used for complex or multiple mapping (please see Section 2.2 'Attribute mapping cases') and an empty colored square will appear next to it (Figure 10, point 3).

Figure 10

- it is not mandatory to link all the elements from the national database to the EFSA attributes. Irrelevant attributes from the national file can be left unmapped. A pop-up message will ask the user for confirmation at the end of the mapping (Figure 11).

Figure 11

- In case of accidental erroneous mapping, the user can right-click on the EFSA attribute and click on 'Revert' to undo the linking (Figure 12).

Figure 12

- The user can use the ‘**Inherit**’ functionality when exactly the same information from the national database has to be repeated in two different EFSA attributes that belong to different hierarchically entities of the same activity.

Example: in the animal population activity, the same information about the unique identifier of the establishment and its geo-location from the ESTABLISHMENT entity can be inherited in the subunit and its geo-location in the SUBUNIT entity. The users can right-click on the EFSA attribute, choose the ‘Inherit’ option and select the relevant attribute from which they want to inherit the information.

Please note: the ‘Inherit’ option cannot be used when:

- two attributes belong in the same entity
- the information to be inherited belongs hierarchically in the lower-level entity than the attribute of interest (Figure 13)

Figure 13

- In case that optional EFSA attributes do not match with names in the national database, the user can right-click on the EFSA attribute and select the choice 'Not available'. The attribute will be excluded from the mapping (Figure 14).

Figure 14

2.2. Attribute mapping cases

There are three types of attribute mapping the users can perform: (1) simple match, (2) complex match and (3) multiple match:

1. **[simple match]:** When an EFSA attribute perfectly corresponds to one attribute present in the national database (i.e., “1 to 1” relationship between the national names and the EFSA attributes).

Example: The attribute [subUnitId] from the EFSA pig population data model can be linked to a single attribute in the national database (“subCode”). In this case, the user simply drags the national name from the left side and drops it on the EFSA attribute on the right below (Figure 15).

Please note: This is the **only** type of mapping applicable to attributes with no catalogues associated.

Figure 15

2. **[complex match]:** When the national data are characterised by a **higher degree of aggregation** than the EFSA SIGMA data model (i.e., “1 to many” relationship between the national names and the EFSA attributes).

Example: The attributes [subUnitSpecies] and [subUnitPurpType] from the EFSA pig population data model might be covered by **one single name in the national database**. In this case, the user needs to drop the national name (e.g., “species_purp”) in all the EFSA attributes that are covered by that single attribute (Figure 16).

Please note: This type of mapping is only applicable to attributes linked to catalogues.

Figure 16

3. **[multiple match]:** When the national data are characterised by a **lower degree of aggregation** than the EFSA data model (i.e., “many to 1” relationship between the national names and the EFSA attributes).

Example: The attribute “estabType” from the EFSA pig population data model might be described by more than one names in the national database. In this case the users must drop all the relevant attributes (e.g., “type1, type2”), on the corresponding EFSA attribute, e.g., “estabType” (Figure 17).

Please note: This type of mapping is only applicable to attributes linked to catalogues.

Figure 17

2.3. Edit

In the case that the users want to edit their existing mapping, they should follow the steps below:

1. Click on the **Map** tab and then on **Entity**
2. Select from the drop-down menu the activity of interest (e.g., Pig-Population).
3. A pop-up message box will appear asking the users if they want to edit the existing mapping or to delete the current one and start from scratch.
4. Click on the “Edit Mapping” button to modify the current mapping (Figure 18).

Figure 18

5. The tool will transfer the users in the drag and drop stage of the attribute mapping, in the initial overview table.
6. Click on the ‘Next’ button to access the existing mapping,
7. Right-click on any attribute is necessary to be corrected to revert the current mapping and implement any corrections.
8. **The user has also the possibility to add a new national attribute by writing in the tab the name of the attribute and press ‘Enter’ (Figure 19, Actions 1 and 2).** Note that the only special symbol allowed is the dot.
9. The new attribute will be displayed at the bottom of the list of national attributes (Figure 19, Action 3). You can now map the newly added attribute.
10. Click on the ‘Next’ button to confirm the mapping. The summary mapping table will be displayed (you can always revert to the previous stage by clicking on the

Previous’ button). Click on the ‘Next’ button at the bottom of the summary table to confirm the mapping.

Please note: In the case the users modify the mapping of attributes associated with catalogues, the existing catalogue mapping will be deleted and should be performed again to map the new associated values (see Section 3 ‘CATALOGUE MAPPING’). The tool will ask for confirmation to proceed, and the user will have to click ‘Yes’ on the ‘Force the mapping’ button at the bottom of the summary table (Figure 19).

Figure 19

11. Click on ‘Finish’ to generate the new schema. A pop-up message will appear reminding the users to remap the new associated catalogue values (Figure 20).

Figure 20

3. CATALOGUE MAPPING

3.1. General instructions

Once the users have completed their attribute mapping, they should proceed with the catalogue

mapping of their values. In the case the users have chosen the automatic upload of their data from the national file at the final stage of the attribute mapping (default option of the tool), the values will be available and visible for catalogue mapping effective immediately (Figure 9).

If the users choose not to upload their national data, a manual typing of each national value must be implemented. Other than that, the process remains the same.

Please note: The users cannot proceed to the catalogue mapping if the attribute mapping has not been completed (see Section 2.2 '[Attribute mapping cases](#)').

The users should follow the steps below to complete their catalogue mapping:

1. Click on the **Map** tab and then on **Catalogue** (Figure 21, action 1).
2. Choose the activity of interest (e.g., Pig-Population) (action 2).
3. Choose the entity from the drop-down list. The associated catalogues of the attributes that need to be mapped will appear (action 3).
4. The user can open each catalogue by clicking on the green 'Edit' button.

Figure 21

3.2. Catalogue mapping cases

Based on the type of relationship between attributes (see Section 2.2 'Attribute mapping cases'), the users need to perform the catalogue mapping in a slightly different way.

1. **[simple match]:** "1 to 1" relationship between the national names and the EFSA attributes
 - Open the EFSA SIGMA catalogue of interest by clicking on the green button 'Show catalogues', next to the attribute (Figure 21, action 3).
 - The uploaded values associated with the catalogue will appear in a table in the bottom and will be visible in the left column, titled with the respective name from the national file (Figure 22, point 1). In case the user has chosen not to upload the values automatically, each value must be typed in the left column of the table.
 - Click on the 'Edit' button for the first combination of national and EFSA values (action 2).
 - Choose from the drop-down list the relevant value to be mapped from the EFSA catalogue and click on the 'Save' button (action 3).
 - Repeat the process for each national value, and then for each catalogue.

Figure 22

Please note: in case of manual typing for the catalogue values, if two (or more) national values of the same attribute correspond to one EFSA catalogue value., one separate line must be inserted in the catalogue mapping for each one of the catalogue terms and all of them should be mapped to the same EFSA value.

Example: if there are two different ways to indicate a farm in the national database (e.g., **FARMA** and **farm**), when mapping the values for the attribute Type of establishment [estabType], the user should

insert one line for **FARMA** and one separate line for **farm** and select for both the EFSA catalogue value **Farm** from the drop-down menu (Figure 23).

estabType	ESTABLISHMENT TYPE	Operations
FARMA	Farm	
farm	Farm	

Prev **1** Next

Figure 23

- [complex match]:** “1 to many” relationship between the national names and the EFSA attributes. The users need to combine a single piece of information to match with two values of the EFSA catalogue.

Example: The national name ‘speciespurp’ covers two EFSA SIGMA attributes [subunit species and subunit purpose type].

- Open the associated EFSA catalogues by clicking on the green ‘Show catalogues’ button, next to the complex mapped attribute.
- The uploaded values associated with each catalogue will appear in a table in the bottom and will be visible in the left column, titled with the respective name from the national file (Figure 24, point 1).
- Click on the ‘Edit’ button for the first combination of national and EFSA values (action 2)
- Click on the first EFSA catalogue (action 3) and select the value of interest (e.g., **Pig (as animal)**).

List of Catalogue Values

1	speciespurp	SPECIES	3	SUBUNIT PURPOSE TYPE	Operations
→	pig meat	Select Catalogue Value	↓	Select Catalogue Value	
→	pig mixed	Wild boar (as animal) Pig (as animal) Boar;pig hybrid (as animal)			

Figure 24

- Click on the second EFSA catalogue (Figure 25, action 1) and select the value of interest (e.g., **Meat/Fattening**).
- Click on the ‘Save’ button (action 2).
- Repeat the process for each national value, and then for each catalogue.

Figure 25

3. **[multiple match]:** “many to 1” relationship between the national names and the EFSA attributes. The users need to combine two pieces of information to match with a single value of the EFSA catalogue.

Example: The two national names ‘type1’ and ‘type2’ cover one EFSA attribute ‘type of establishment’ (estabType).

- Open the associated EFSA catalogue by clicking on the green ‘Show catalogues’ button, next to the multiple mapped attribute.
- The uploaded values associated with the catalogue will appear in a table in the bottom and will be visible in the left column, titled with the respective name from the national file (e.g., **farma** for ‘type’ and **centre** for ‘type2’) (**Error! Reference source not found.**).
- Click on the ‘Edit’ button for the first combination of national and EFSA values (Figure 26, action 1).
- Click on the EFSA catalogue (action 2) and select the one value of interest from the drop-down list, associated with the two values (e.g., **Farm**).
- Click on the ‘Save’ button (action 3).
- Repeat the process for each national value with multiple mapping, and then for each catalogue.

Important tips

- The users can edit an existing or a new value by clicking on the ‘Edit’ blue button under **Operations** column (Figure 27, action 1).
- The users can delete a value by clicking on the red button under **Operations** column (action 2).

- The users can add a new value by clicking on the (+) blue button on the bottom of **Operations** column (action 3).
- In case of multiple catalogue values to be mapped (e.g., NUTS3 area of the establishment, from the pig population EFSA data model), the users can download the EFSA catalogue in an Excel format (action 4-5):
 - Click on the 'Download File' button, provide their own values in the first column of the file and save it.
 - Click on 'Upload File' button and select the configured file, click on the upload icon with the name of the file, and click on the 'Confirm' button.
 - A message should pop-up confirming the successful insertion and all the values should appear mapped to the correspondent EFSA catalogue values.

Figure 26

4. FILE TRANSLATION

Once the users have performed the attribute mapping and the catalogue mapping, the SIGMA EST mapping tool is configured and ready to translate the national files. In this section, guidelines are provided to the users, on how to translate their national files into XML files, fit to the EFSA standards. The users should follow the steps below:

1. Click on the **Map** tab and then click on **Translate file** (Figure 28, action 1-2).
2. Click on the 'XLS' button (or 'XML', depending on the format of the extracted file from the national database) and select the activity of interest from the drop-down menu. The 'Upload file' button will be activated (actions 3-4).
3. Click on the 'Upload file' button and select the file containing the national data to be translated (action 5).

Figure 27

4. Click on the button with the upload icon and the name of the national file to complete the upload (Figure 29). A message will appear confirming the successful upload.

Figure 28

5. Click on the 'Check' button. A pop-up message will appear, confirming the successful checks for the file structure (Figure 30, action 1).

Figure 29

6. Click on the 'Convert file' button (Figure 30, action 1). A pop-up message will appear, confirming the scheduling of the translation. The user will be notified with an email at the end of the translation process.

Figure 30

5. DOWNLOAD OF THE TRANSLATED XML FILE

Once the translation of the national file has been completed, the users should receive a notification email. In order to download their translated XML file and/or check for necessary corrections, the users should follow the steps below:

1. Click on the bell icon on the top right corner, there should be a notification.
2. A table will appear with your national file sent for translation and information regarding the status of the process, the organization, the activity, the identification number, the filename, the elaboration date, the output type, the merge function and a last column with buttons (Figure 31):
 - Yellow button: containing the translated file in xml format
 - Blue button: if existing, containing the log file with errors that need to be checked and corrected. **Please note, in this case the users must implement their corrections and repeat the national file translation process** (Figure 31, case 1)
 - Red button: indicating the possibility for the users to delete their files
3. Click on the filename to download the original national file uploaded for translation.
4. Provided that there is no blue button indicating errors that should be fixed, click on the yellow button to download the translated XML file (Figure 31, case 2).
5. The user can choose to download xml files individually or in bulk. In the second case, the user can merge xml files belonging to the same activity (e.g., ASF laboratory) and characterized by the same output type (e.g., Standard or Amendment). Please note that only xml files without errors can be merged for further download.
6. Proceed with uploading the XML file in the relevant data collection's folder in EFSA's Data Collection Framework (DCF).

You are connected as EFSA on Sigma Project

List of Your Files

Status	Organization	Activity name	Id	Original Excel file Filename	Uploaded Date	Elaboration Date	Output		
							Type	XML file	Log file
	EFSA	AI-Laboratory	1447	SIGMA_EST_AI_training_laboratory_dummy_data.xlsx	19/09/2024, 2:46 PM	19/09/2024, 2:46 PM (< 1 minutes)	Standard	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	EFSA	Poultry-Population	1446	SIGMA_EST_AI_training_poultry_pop_dummy_data.xlsx	19/09/2024, 9:21 AM	19/09/2024, 9:21 AM (< 1 minutes)	Standard	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	EFSA	AI-Laboratory	1445	SIGMA_EST_AI_training_laboratory_dummy_data.xlsx	19/09/2024, 9:10 AM	19/09/2024, 9:10 AM (< 1 minutes)	Standard	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Figure 31

- **Please note:** if users have not received any notification two hours after completing the translation, they should:
 - Check their 'Spam' folder;
 - Send an email to the sigma-est.support@izs.it functional mailbox.

6. AMENDMENT

Amendment is a process that allows data providers to modify records of datasets that have been already accepted in DCF and have reached their final state in EFSA's Data Warehouse (DWH). The amendments process is performed **at a record level**. Therefore, if an amendment is necessary, the data provider shall create a new excel file including all the records that must be updated or deleted, **using the same record identifiers that have been already submitted in the DCF**. Based on this, there are two kind of amendments that can be performed:

- Amend update:
 - This operation is used to update records in the EFSA DWH. **In this case, the records to be updated must be included in the excel file to be uploaded in the SIGMA EST, with all the variables filled in as already submitted and the new values updated in the relevant columns.**
 - This operation will result in a new version of the record in the EFSA DWH.
- Amend delete:
 - This operation is used to delete accepted records in the EFSA DWH. **In this case, the records to be deleted should be included in the excel file to be uploaded in the SIGMA EST, as they were submitted in the DCF.**
 - This operation will result in the deletion of the record in the EFSA DWH.

Once the excel file with the records to be amended is ready, the users should follow the steps below (Figure 32):

Figure 32

1. Click on the 'Map' tab and select 'Amendment' (Figure 32, Actions 1 and 2).
2. Choose the format of your file for the uploading step (action 3).
3. Choose the entity from the drop-down list (action 4).
4. Select the type of Amendment you want to perform by selecting either the button

- 'Amendments Update' or 'Amendments Delete' (action 5).
5. Click on the 'Upload file' button and select the file containing the national data to be amended (action 6).
 6. Proceed with uploading the XML file in the relevant data collection's folder in DCF.

Glossary

SIGMA EST	EFSA
Activity	A specific data model (e.g., the Pig Population data model in the context of the ASF data collection)
Entity	Conceptual group of attributes
Attribute	Variable in a dataset
Catalogue	List of predefined values created by EFSA. It can be associated to one or more attributes.